

0.04

0.07

0.05

0.07

USCO75_abs75_ASTRAL

2.0

0.07

0.05

USCO90_ASTRAL

0.9

0.05

0.05

USCO90_abs75_ASTRAL

2.0

0.04

USCO100_GHOST

0.06

0.05

USCO100_ASTRAL

0.9

0.05

0.07

USCO100_abs75_GHOST

USCO100_abs75_ASTRAL

2.0

0.07

UCE50_abs70_GHOST

0.07

UCE75_partitioning

0.07

0.07

UCE75_abs70_GHOST

0.07

UCE75_abs70_ASTRAL

2.0

UCE90_GHOST

0.06

UCE90_ASTRAL

0.9

UCE90_abs70_GHOST

0.06

UCE90_abs70_ASTRAL

